

Modelling and Control of a 5DoF Tilting Quadrotor

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Abstract—The inherent underactuation of standard multirotors has led to the development of new platform designs, especially for physical aerial interaction. This paper presents the modelling and control of a tilting quadrotor, which includes tilting motors actuated by two servomotors. This design allows independent control of the pitch angle and the x-axis position by the reorientation of the motors. In this paper, we derive the dynamics of the aerial robot in a state-space representation, including its allocation matrix. This model is compared with that of an underactuated quadrotor, showing the possibility of controlling the pitch angle and the x-axis position in an independent way. For controlling the tilting quadrotor, the standard PID-cascade controller of an underactuated quadrotor is adapted for the platform with servomotors. Finally, the controller is validated through extensive simulations. The proposed model and controller serve as a first step in the development of a 5DoF tilting quadrotor.

Video available at <https://youtu.be/eXVDa9SZGIQ>.

Index Terms—Aerial Robotics, Aerial Physical Interaction, Tilting Quadrotor

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have seen a significant rise in popularity and application over the past decade. They are widely used in various fields such as aerial photography, environmental monitoring, agriculture, and delivery services. The versatility, maneuverability, and cost-effectiveness of UAVs make them ideal for tasks ranging from simple recreational use to complex industrial applications [1]. The capability to perform precise and stable flights has also opened up opportunities for UAVs in search and rescue operations [2], infrastructure inspection [3], and surveillance [4].

Moreover, certain applications require UAVs to perform contact-based operations, necessitating physical interaction with their environment [5]. These applications include tasks such as maintenance and inspection of structures [6], fruit harvesting [7], construction, and even medical delivery where precise placement is crucial. In these scenarios, precision in contact and the ability to manipulate objects or apply force without causing damage are essential for the successful

execution of these tasks. However, traditional multirotors, with their standard underactuated design, face limitations in such scenarios [8]. Their inability to independently control attitude and translational movement restricts their effectiveness in performing complex tasks that require precise positioning and contact.

To address these challenges, several designs have been proposed in recent years. In [9], a fully-actuated platform with tilted propellers is presented. This platform allows 6DoF (Degrees of Freedom) movements but is limited in attitude control [10]. In [11], an omnidirectional platform with eight tilted bidirectional rotors allows 6DoF trajectories in any orientation. However, the tilted propeller designs have lower performance, as in hover position the lateral forces of the motors are compensated, reducing the flight time compared with the coplanar configuration [12]. Due to this, other works propose the use of tilting motors actuated by servomotors, which allow reconfiguration from an underactuated configuration when the platform needs to hover, to a fully-actuated [13] or to an omnidirectional [14] configuration when it has to move. Other designs achieve omnidirectionality in only one direction while remaining underactuated in the other. This reduces the number of actuators needed but still allows for precise and stable contact through the omnidirectional direction [15]. Some of these designs have led companies to perform inspections in refineries [16].

A. Contributions and novelties

This work presents the modelling and control of a tilting quadrotor capable of performing 5DoF movements. The aerial platform is equipped with two servomotors that allow the rotors to rotate in pairs, similar to the design developed in [15]. Compared to [15], our work modifies the standard PID-cascade controller of a quadrotor to accommodate the tilting quadrotor based on our developed model, avoiding the need for a specific controller that could be computationally demanding. This work serves as a first step towards the development of a 5DoF tilting quadrotor using open-source autopilots, which are based on PID cascade controllers and are easy to modify. We propose the following contributions:

- Modelling of a quadrotor with two servomotors for tilting the rotors and its comparison with the standard underactuated quadrotor.

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- Adaptation of a standard PID-cascade controller for the tilting quadrotor for 5DoF flights.

The proposed model and controller are validated through simulations using the GRVC simulator [17], which has been modified to include the tilting quadrotor.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II and Section III cover the quadrotor description and its dynamic model, including the aerial platform dynamics and the allocation matrix. Section IV presents the control of the platform and its comparison with a standard quadrotor. Section V validates the proposed controller through extensive simulations. Finally, Section VI summarizes the conclusions of the paper and propose future works.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The aerial platform used in this work is based on a quadrotor with H-configuration, as shown in Figure 1. This platform is composed of four motors that are arranged on a H-frame, with a distance between motors of $2L_x$ on the x_B axis and $2L_y$ on the y_B axis. In addition, we consider that the motors can be tilted around y_B -axis by pairs thanks to two servomotors. Motor 1 and motor 2 are tilted an angle β_1 by the first servomotor while motor 3 and motor 4 are tilted an angle β_2 by the second servomotor. Figure 1c shows both rotations. We suppose that the servomotors have an angle reference interface, and that we can directly command the desired tilt angle. This is easy to obtain using smartservomotors such as Herkulex or Dynamixel, which have internal controllers. In the case of the motors, we consider that they have a spin reference interface, as we use ESCs for the brushless motors.

III. MODELLING

A. Aerial Platform Dynamics

We define a world frame denoted by \mathcal{F}_W , with its origin O_W and its axes x_W, y_W, z_W . We also define a body frame \mathcal{F}_B located at the center of mass of the quadrotor, and with axis x_B, y_B, z_B . Moreover, we define four motor frames $\mathcal{F}_{M_i} \forall i \in [1, 2, 3, 4]$, with its origin O_{M_i} and its axes y_{M_i} parallel to y_B and z_{M_i} perpendicular to the propeller i . Figure 1a shows the tilting quadrotor, including the frames \mathcal{F}_W and \mathcal{F}_B .

We denote by $\mathbf{p} = [x, y, z]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the position of the quadrotor w.r.t. \mathcal{F}_W , while $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the linear speed expressed in \mathcal{F}_W . In addition, the orientation of the quadrotor is expressed using the roll-pitch-yaw angles vector $\boldsymbol{\eta} = [\phi, \theta, \psi]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$, which represents the rotation of \mathcal{F}_B w.r.t. \mathcal{F}_W . This orientation is also represented by the rotation matrix ${}^W\mathbf{R}_B$. Moreover, $\boldsymbol{\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the angular velocity of the object w.r.t. \mathcal{F}_W expressed in \mathcal{F}_B . The state vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{18}$ of the system is composed of:

$$\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{p}^T, \boldsymbol{\eta}^T, \mathbf{v}^T, \boldsymbol{\omega}^T, \boldsymbol{\omega}_R^T, \boldsymbol{\beta}_S^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{18}, \quad (1)$$

which includes the spin velocity of the brushless motors $\boldsymbol{\omega}_R = [\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4]^T \in \mathbb{R}^4$ and the angle of the servomotors $\boldsymbol{\beta}_S = [\beta_1, \beta_2]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The control input of

(a) World frame, body fram and tilting quadrotor.

(b) Motor numeration.

(c) β_1 and β_2 angles.

Fig. 1: Tilting quadrotor platform: frames, motor numerations and β_S angles.

the system $\mathbf{u} = [\boldsymbol{\omega}_R^{ref\top}, \boldsymbol{\beta}_S^{ref\top}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is composed by the spin velocity reference of the brushless motors $\boldsymbol{\omega}_R^{ref} = [\omega_1^{ref}, \omega_2^{ref}, \omega_3^{ref}, \omega_4^{ref}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^4$ and the reference angle of the servomotors $\boldsymbol{\beta}_S^{ref} = [\beta_1^{ref}, \beta_2^{ref}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$. With all this, the system dynamics can be expressed in the space-state form $\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u})$ as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{v}, \quad (2a)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}} = \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\omega}, \quad (2b)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}} = \frac{1}{m}({}^W\mathbf{R}_B\mathbf{f}_R - mg\mathbf{z}_W), \quad (2c)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} = \mathbf{J}_B^{-1}(-\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{J}_B\boldsymbol{\omega} - \boldsymbol{\tau}_R), \quad (2d)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_R = \frac{1}{\tau_M}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_R^{ref} - \boldsymbol{\omega}_R), \quad (2e)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_S = \frac{1}{\tau_S}(\boldsymbol{\beta}_S^{ref} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_S), \quad (2f)$$

where $\mathbf{T} \in SO(3)$ is the transformation matrix that relates the angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ with the angle derivatives $\dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}$, $\mathbf{J}_B \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the inertia matrix of the quadrotor and $m \in \mathbb{R}^+$ its mass. The brushless motors and the servomotors are modeled as a first order system with time constant τ_M and τ_S , respectively. In addition, $\mathbf{f}_R \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are the force and torque applied to the quadrotor, and expressed in \mathcal{F}_B . Both depend

on the spin velocity of the motors $\boldsymbol{\omega}_R$ and the servo angles β_S .

This model represents the general dynamic of an aerial platform. The main difference between the different platforms designs is in the generation of the force \mathbf{f}_R and torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R$. The generation of this force and torque for the tilting quadrotor is explained in Section III-B.

B. Allocation Matrix

The allocation matrix $\mathbf{H}(\beta_S) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 4}$ relates the spin velocity of the motors $\boldsymbol{\omega}_R$ and the servo angles β_S , with the force \mathbf{f}_R and torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R$ applied to the quadrotor body as:

$$[\mathbf{f}_R^\top, \boldsymbol{\tau}_R^\top]^\top = \mathbf{H}(\beta_S) \boldsymbol{\omega}_R^2, \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega}_R^2 = [\omega_1^2, \omega_2^2, \omega_3^2, \omega_4^2]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4$. This relation can be derived by considering the individual thrust and torques of the motors. In this work, we consider that the motor thrust $\mathbf{T}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and the drag torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ follows a quadratic model with the spin velocity. The model, expressed in the motor frame \mathcal{F}_{M_i} , is represented as:

$$\mathbf{T}_i = [0, 0, k_f \omega_i^2]^\top \text{ and } \boldsymbol{\tau}_i = [0, 0, (-1)^{i+1} k_d \omega_i^2]^\top, \quad (4)$$

where k_f is the thrust factor and k_d is the drag factor of the propeller. In addition, the factor $(-1)^{i+1}$ is used since half of the propellers rotate clockwise and the other half rotates counter-clockwise. Considering this, the total force \mathbf{f}_R and total torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R$ are discussed in detail below.

1) *Force generation*: Considering the four motors of the platform, the total force is computed by:

$$\mathbf{f}_R = \sum_{i=1}^4 {}^B \mathbf{R}_{P_i} \mathbf{T}_i, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{T}_i is the thrust generated by motor i and ${}^B \mathbf{R}_{P_i}$ is the rotation matrix from the motor frame \mathcal{F}_M to body frame \mathcal{F}_B . This matrix is computed considering the rotation of the servos as ${}^B \mathbf{R}_{P_i} = \mathbf{R}_Y(\alpha_i)$, where \mathbf{R}_Y is the rotation matrix around y_B -axis and α_i the rotated angle. As presented in Section II, the motors are rotated with $\alpha_1 = \alpha_3 = \beta_1$ and $\alpha_2 = \alpha_4 = \beta_2$.

2) *Torque generation*: The total torque is produced by the thrust and by the drag force of the propellers as:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_R = \sum_{i=1}^4 \underbrace{({}^B \mathbf{p}_i \times {}^B \mathbf{R}_{P_i} \mathbf{T}_i)}_{\boldsymbol{\tau}_{\text{thrust}}} + \underbrace{{}^B \mathbf{R}_{P_i} \boldsymbol{\tau}_i}_{\boldsymbol{\tau}_{\text{drag}}}. \quad (6)$$

Finally, considering that $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \beta_1$, $\alpha_3 = \alpha_4 = \beta_2$, the rotation sense presented in Section II, Eq. (6) and Eq. (5),

$$\mathbf{H}(\beta_S) = \begin{bmatrix} k_f s \beta_1 & k_f s \beta_1 & k_f s \beta_2 & k_f s \beta_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ k_f c \beta_1 & k_f c \beta_1 & k_f c \beta_2 & k_f c \beta_2 \\ k_t s \beta_1 - L_y k_f c \beta_1 & -k_t s \beta_1 + L_y k_f c \beta_1 & k_t s \beta_2 + L_y k_f c \beta_2 & -k_t s \beta_2 - L_y k_f c \beta_2 \\ -L_x k_f c \beta_1 & -L_x k_f c \beta_1 & L_x k_f c \beta_2 & L_x k_f c \beta_2 \\ k_t c \beta_1 + L_y k_f s \beta_1 & -k_t c \beta_1 - L_y k_f s \beta_1 & k_t c \beta_2 - L_y k_f s \beta_2 & -k_t c \beta_2 + L_y k_f s \beta_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

the allocation matrix can be identified. Eq. (7) presents the allocation matrix, where s is the sine function, c is the cosine function, and L_x and L_y are the distances from the center of gravity of the platform to the motor position in the x_B -axis and y_B -axis, respectively. In the case of a standard quadrotor, the allocation matrix can be obtained by evaluating Eq. (7) with $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0^\circ$.

This matrix shows that the tilting quadrotor can generate lateral force f_x by modifying the tilting angles β_1 and β_2 .

The first row, related with the generated force f_x , is not null if $\beta_{1,2} \neq n\pi$, $\forall n \in \mathbb{Z}$. This allows us to control the pitch angle θ through $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R$ and the x-axis position through \mathbf{f}_R when tilting the servomotors. In the case of standard quadrotor where $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0^\circ$, the first row is null. This causes the platform to modify its pitch angle in order to control its x_B -axis position. Furthermore, the second row of the matrix is null, so the platform can not generate lateral force on the y_B -axis. Due to this, the behaviour of the platform in the y_B -axis is similar to the one of a standard configuration, as it has to modified its roll angle for controlling the y_B -axis position. In conclusion, the tilting quadrotor can control 5DoF independently as the pitch angle and the x_B -axis position are now decoupled.

IV. CONTROL

The controller of the tilting platform is based on the standard quadrotor controller, which has been modified for considering the possibility of controlling 5DoF. This section first presents the standard quadrotor controller and then details the modifications introduced to apply it to the 5DoF tilting quadrotor.

A. Standard quadrotor controller

The standard quadrotor controller is composed of the position controller, the attitude controller, the attitude η_{Ref} generator, and the motor mixer, as shown in Figure 2a. Although there are different position and attitude controllers such as MPC, geometric, backstepping, etc., we decide to use the standard PID cascade [18] for both controllers, as it is the most known and used for aerial platforms. Furthermore, we rely on a PID cascade controller because most autopilots use it, making it the easiest option for future implementations. The different parts of the controller are explained below.

1) *Position controller*: The position controller computes the desired force of the rotors \mathbf{f}_R for tracking the trajectory \mathbf{p}_{Ref} . Eq. (8) presents the position controller:

Fig. 2: Comparison between the controllers of the standard quadrotor and the tilting quadrotor with servomotors. The differences are the control actions of the servomotors, the pitch reference θ_{Ref} and the control of the servomotors. The differences are marked with a pink background on Fig. 2b.

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{v}_{Ref} = PID(\mathbf{p}_{Ref} - \mathbf{p}) + \dot{\mathbf{p}}_{Ref}, \\ \mathbf{a}_{Ref} = PID(\mathbf{v}_{Ref} - \dot{\mathbf{p}}) + \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_{Ref} + g\mathbf{z}_W, \\ \mathbf{f}_R = m\mathbf{a}_{Ref}, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where the function $PID(\cdot)$ implements a parallel PID controller.

2) *Calculation of the desired orientation*: the desired orientation $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{Ref}$ is computed as a rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_r = [\mathbf{x}_r, \mathbf{y}_r, \mathbf{z}_r]$, where the vectors \mathbf{x}_r , \mathbf{y}_r and \mathbf{z}_r are:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{z}_r = \frac{\mathbf{f}_R}{\|\mathbf{f}_R\|} \\ \mathbf{y}_r = \frac{\mathbf{z}_r \times [c_{\psi_r}, s_{\psi_r}, 0]^T}{\|\mathbf{z}_r \times [c_{\psi_r}, s_{\psi_r}, 0]^T\|} \\ \mathbf{x}_r = \mathbf{y}_r \times \mathbf{z}_r. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The roll and pitch reference are obtained as $\phi_r = \arctan(r_{32}/r_{33})$ and $\theta_r = -\arcsin(r_{31})$, where r_{ij} is the element (i, j) of the matrix \mathbf{R}_r .

3) *Attitude controller*: The attitude controller computes the desired torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R$, for tracking the desired attitude $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{Ref}$ as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\omega}_{Ref} = \mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\eta})(PID(\boldsymbol{\eta}_{Ref} - \boldsymbol{\eta}) + \dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_{Ref}) \\ \boldsymbol{\zeta}_{Ref} = PID(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{Ref} - \boldsymbol{\omega}) + \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_{Ref} \\ \boldsymbol{\tau}_R = \mathbf{J}_B \boldsymbol{\zeta}_{Ref} + \boldsymbol{\omega} \times (\mathbf{J}_B \boldsymbol{\omega}). \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

4) *Motor mixer*: Finally, the spin velocities $\boldsymbol{\omega}^{Ref}$ are computed with the allocation matrix and with the thrust F_Z and total torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R$ computed by the controllers. For doing this, the allocation matrix \mathbf{H} is inverted, without considering the two first arrows, as they are null. Doing this, the matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$ is constant and its inverse can be computed only once.

B. 5DoF tilting quadrotor controller

The tilting quadrotor controller is obtained by modifying the standard controller. The changes introduced are:

- **Trajectory generator**: as explained in Section III, the pitch angle and the x-axis position can be controlled independently. Due to this, the trajectory generator now commands a pitch reference.

- **Servomotor angle β_S from \mathbf{f}_R** : this block computes the servomotor angles based on the desired force. Although we can control β_1 and β_2 independently, we choose $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta$ as it minimizes the control action, as shown in [15]. The angle β is computed as $\beta = \text{atan}(f_z/f_x)$.
- **$\boldsymbol{\eta}_{Ref}$ generator**: in this configuration, the only angle reference computed is the roll reference ϕ_{Ref} , as it is needed for controlling the y-axis position. This angle is computed as $\phi_{Ref} = -\text{atan}(f_z/f_y)$.
- **Motor mixer**: this matrix now depends on the servomotor angles β_S . It is computed during the control cycle with by the allocation matrix $\mathbf{H}(\beta_S)$. We use the pseudoinverse as $\mathbf{H}(\beta_S)$ has not full rank. Furthermore, the servomotor references β_S^{Ref} are directly send to the servomotors, as shown in Figure 2b.

V. RESULTS

The proposed controller is validated with simulations in Matlab/Simulink, modifying for that the GRVC simulator [17]. Three different experiments have been tested. For the two first experiments trajectory moves first 1 m in the x-axis and then 1 m in the y-axis, with $\theta_{Ref} = 0^\circ$ for the first simulation and $\theta_{Ref} = 45^\circ$ for the second. In the third experiment the platform maintains its position while performing a full rotation around the y-axis. The parameters of the simulation are shown in Table I.

TABLE I: Parameters of the simulations

Parameter	Value
UAV mass, m	1.787 kg
Inertia matrix, \mathbf{J}_B	diag([0.030, 0.029, 0.054]) kg m ²
Brushless motor time constant, τ_M	0.05 s
Servomotor motor time constant, τ_S	0.15 s
Motor to center distances, L_x, L_y	$L_x = 0.198$ m, $L_y = 0.198$ m
Thrust factor of the propeller, k_f	$3.146 \cdot 10^{-6}$ N/(rad/s) ²
Drag factor of the propeller, k_d	$3.146 \cdot 10^{-7}$ Nm/(rad/s) ²

A. Coplanar trajectory

The objective of this first simulation is to illustrate how the tilting rotors enable the UAV to move in the \mathbf{x}_B direction

Fig. 3: XY position during the coplanar trajectory. The left axis represents the XY position of the UAV, while the right axis represents the roll and pitch angle during the trajectory. During this movement, the pitch reference is $\theta_{Ref} = 0^\circ$.

Fig. 4: Servomotor angle during the coplanar trajectory.

without the need of modifying the pitch angle. During the trajectory the pitch reference is $\theta_{Ref} = 0^\circ$.

Figure 3 shows that the movement along the x-axis is decoupled from the pitch rotation, whereas the displacement along the y-axis still depends on the roll angle, as it is modified for tracking the trajectory. Furthermore, the maximal error during the trajectory are $e_x = 0.012$ m and $e_y = 0.118$ m. These errors show that the platform is more precise on the x-axis movement than on the y-axis movement, due to the decoupling between pitch angle and x-axis movement.

In addition, Figure 4 shows the servomotor angle β during the trajectory. It demonstrates that, when moving along the x-axis, the servomotors rotate to generate the necessary force for the displacement. However, when the platform moves along the y-axis, a roll rotation is needed, as the servomotors remain vertical due to their inability to produce force on the y_B direction.

B. Tilted trajectory

The second experiment aims to show that the platform can fly with a tilted orientation in the pitch angle $\theta \neq 0^\circ$, due to the decoupling of the pitch rotation and the x-axis translation. In this simulation, the trajectory was the same as

Fig. 5: XY position during the tilted trajectory. The left axis represents the XY position of the UAV, while the right axis represents the roll and pitch angle during the trajectory. During this movement, the pitch reference is $\theta_{Ref} = 45^\circ$.

Fig. 6: Servomotor angle during the tilted trajectory.

in the coplanar trajectory, with the difference that the pitch reference is $\theta_{Ref} = 45^\circ$ from the beginning of the simulation.

Figure 5 shows the trajectory on the left axis, which is the same as in the first simulation. However, the attitude, presented on the right axis, is different as the pitch reference and x-axis position are decoupled, as they can be controlled separately. Furthermore, once again, the errors obtained in the x-axis movement $e_x = 0.047$ m are smaller than those in the y-axis movement $e_x = 0.196$ m due to the decoupling between pitch angle and x-axis position.

Moreover, Figure 6 presents the servomotor angle β during the simulation. For a displacement along the x-axis, the servomotors rotate to move while maintaining the desired pitch angle. Then, the y-axis movement is achieved by a rotation in roll, as shown in Figure 5, with some corrections introduced by the servomotors to control the x position. Finally, during the hover position ($t > 6$ s), the angle is $\beta = -45^\circ$ due to the pitch angle $\theta = 45^\circ$.

C. Pitch rotation while hold position

The goal of this simulation is to demonstrate how the UAV is able to perform a full rotation by controlling the pitch

Fig. 7: Position error during the pitch rotation trajectory.

Fig. 8: Servomotor angle during the pitch rotation trajectory.

angle while remaining in the same position. This rotation is performed in 5 s.

Figure 7 shows the low position errors during the rotation, indicating that the UAV maintains the same position. However, a slight increase in the error of the z-axis position is noticeable when the drone approaches $\theta = 90^\circ$. This loss of height is caused by alignment of the motors when $\beta = -90^\circ$.

Finally, Figure 8 presents the servomotor angle during the rotation. It shows as $\beta = -\theta$, as it is necessary only to generate f_z to maintain the altitude.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented the modelling and control of a tilting quadrotor with capabilities of 5DoF movements. First, the dynamic model was derived and compared with that of a standard configuration, demonstrating that the proposed platform can control the pitch angle and x-axis position independently. Subsequently, the control architecture of a standard quadrotor was modified to enable 5DoF movements with the tilting quadrotor. The controller was validated through simulations, confirming that the platform can perform 5DoF flights. The simulations also revealed that the precision of x-axis movements, achieved by the servomotors, is higher than that of y-axis movements, achieved by rolling. As future work, we propose the construction and validation of the aerial platform and its application in aerial physical interaction.

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